

Title: In Silico Psycho-oncology: Understanding Resilience Pathways in Breast Cancer - Determinants of Longitudinal Depression and Quality of Life Trajectories

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Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S1. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Baseline

Figure S2. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Low Deteriorating QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Month 3

Figure S3. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Low deteriorating QoL trajectory class versus other classes at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Low deteriorating QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S4. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Baseline

Figure S5. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Excellent QoL vs Rest Classes

Scales at Month 3

Figure S6. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with Excellent QoL trajectory class versus other classes at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Excellent QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of other classes.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S7. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovering QoL; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Scales at Baseline

Figure S8. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Recovery vs Moderate QoL

Scales at Month 3

Figure S9. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering QoL trajectory class versus Moderate QoL class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Moderate QoL.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S10. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Baseline

Figure S11. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Stable Moderate/High Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Month 3

Figure S12. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Stable Moderate/High Depression class versus the Resilient Depression trajectory class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S13. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Baseline

Figure S14. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Delayed Occurrence of Depression vs Resilience

Scales at Month 3

Figure S15. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Late Occurrence Depression class versus the Resilient Depression class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Late Occurrence; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Resilient class.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression
Sociodemographics, Lifestyle, Clinical

Figure S16. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for sociodemographic, lifestyle, clinical and cancer-related factors associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression

Scales at Baseline

Figure S17. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at baseline. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.

Recovery vs Stable Moderate/High Depression

Scales at Month 3

Figure S18. Odds ratios (95% CI), adjusted for clinical site, for psychological scales associated with the Recovering Depression class versus the Stable Moderate/High Depression class at month 3. Values >1 indicate higher likelihood of Recovery; values <1 indicate higher likelihood of Stable Moderate/High Depression.